

Synthesis and spectroscopic studies of some new diorganosilicon(IV) and diorganotin(IV) complexes of bidentate Schiff bases having N- and S-donor system

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Abstract : Series of diorganosilicon(IV) and diorganotin(IV) complexes having the formulae $R_2MCl(L^1)$, $R_2MCl(L^2)$, $R_2MCl(L^3)$, $R_2MCl(L^4)$, $R_2M(L^1)_2$, $R_2M(L^2)_2$, $R_2M(L^3)_2$ and $R_2M(L^4)_2$, where M = Si and Sn, R = CH₃, have been synthesized. All the complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance and spectroscopic studies including UV, IR, ¹H, ¹³C, ²⁹Si and ¹¹⁹Sn NMR. On the bases of these studies, the five and six coordinated complexes have been proposed to have trigonal bipyramidal and octahedral geometries respectively.

Keywords : 4-Amino-3-ethyl-5-mercapto-s-triazole, N- and S-donor ligands, silicon-complexes, tin-complexes, spectroscopy.

Introduction

Metal complexes of Schiff bases show biological activities including antibacterial, antifungal, anticancer and herbicidal. Schiff base complexes have also been used in catalytic reactions and as biological models for understanding the structure of biomolecules¹⁻³. The interest in organosilicon(IV) compounds is generated due to their versatile applications in the pharmaceutical and chemical industries. Generally organosilicon compounds seem to have antitumor properties by enhancing the immune defensive system of the organism⁴⁻⁹. The medical applications and effectiveness of the silatranes in the treatment of wounds and tumors are thought to be related to the role of silicon in the growth of epithelial and connective tissues and hair, where its function is to impart strength, elasticity and impermeability to water¹⁰. Similarly increasing attention has been devoted to Schiff base complexes of organotin(IV) in view of their potential applications in medicinal chemistry, biotechnology and their structural variety. Organotin compounds are the active components in a number of biocidal formulations, finding applications in such diverse areas as fungicides, miticides, molluscicides, antifouling paints, surface disinfectants and wood preservatives¹¹. In addition many organotin compounds have been tested for *in vitro* activity against a

large variety of tumor lines and found to be more effective than traditional heavy metal anticancer drugs^{12,13}. Many organotin(IV) complexes show antibacterial activity against gram +ve and gram -ve bacteria and against fungi also^{14,15}. In our laboratory, some organosilicon(IV) and organotin(IV) complexes were synthesized which have been shown to have antibacterial and antifungal activities^{16,17}. So in continuation of our previous work, we have synthesized and characterized some new organosilicon(IV) and organotin(IV) complexes with nitrogen and sulphur donor ligands.

Results and discussion

All the newly synthesized complexes obtained were colored and soluble in DMSO, DMF and MeOH. The molar conductivity values measured for 10⁻³ M solutions in anhydrous DMF are in the range of 10-15 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹; showing that all 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes are non-electrolytic in nature. The range of the conductivity values indicated that the solutions of the complexes are not ionic and all the atoms are present in the coordination sphere. The analytical data are in good agreement with the proposed stoichiometry of the complexes. The physical characteristics and analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical characteristics and analytical data of ligands and their metal complexes

Complex	Empirical formulae (Mol. weight)	Color	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
				C	H	N	S	Si/Sn
L ¹ (EMPCT)	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₅ S (223.29)	Yellow	222	51.49 (51.50)	4.74 (4.72)	30.03 (30.04)	13.74 (13.74)	-
Me ₂ SiCl(L ¹)	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₅ SClSi (325.89)	Light orange	167	44.32 (44.30)	4.88 (4.92)	21.51 (21.53)	20.75 (20.59)	8.54 (8.66)
Me ₂ Si(L ¹) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₁₀ S ₂ Si (552.73)	Orange	171	50.66 (50.57)	4.28 (4.21)	26.76 (26.81)	12.85 (13.05)	5.45 (5.36)
Me ₂ SnCl(L ¹)	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₅ ClSn (416.52)	Light grey	194	34.74 (34.65)	3.85 (3.85)	16.70 (16.84)	16.23 (16.15)	28.48 (28.51)
Me ₂ Sn(L ¹) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₁₀ S ₂ Sn (613.35)	Grey	201	43.22 (43.10)	4.26 (4.24)	22.85 (22.85)	10.33 (10.47)	19.34 (19.34)
L ² (EFMT)	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS (222.27)	Brown	190	48.68 (48.60)	4.56 (4.50)	25.20 (25.22)	21.56 (21.68)	-
Me ₂ SiCl(L ²)	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ N ₄ OSCISi (314.87)	Light yellow	156	42.22 (42.03)	4.70 (4.77)	17.84 (17.83)	26.48 (26.46)	8.76 (8.91)
Me ₂ Si(L ²) ₂	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂ Si (500.67)	Yellow	162	48.33 (48.00)	4.76 (4.80)	22.37 (22.40)	18.99 (19.20)	5.55 (5.60)
Me ₂ SnCl(L ²)	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ N ₄ OSCISn (405.49)	Light brown	214	32.74 (32.63)	3.72 (3.70)	13.68 (13.84)	20.51 (20.54)	29.40 (29.29)
Me ₂ Sn(L ²) ₂	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂ Sn (591.30)	Orange	221	40.65 (40.64)	4.13 (4.06)	18.86 (18.96)	16.14 (16.28)	20.22 (20.06)
L ³ (CBEMT)	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ SCl (266.75)	Light yellow	218	49.43 (49.53)	4.00 (4.12)	12.04 (12.00)	34.53 (34.35)	-
Me ₂ SiCl(L ³)	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ (Cl) ₂ SSi (359.35)	Light green	149	43.68 (43.57)	4.52 (4.46)	15.58 (15.64)	28.38 (28.51)	7.84 (7.82)
Me ₂ Si(L ³) ₂	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₈ S ₂ (Cl) ₂ Si (589.64)	Green	156	49.04 (48.97)	4.41 (4.42)	19.10 (19.04)	22.71 (22.81)	4.74 (4.76)
Me ₂ SnCl(L ³)	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ (Cl) ₂ SSn (449.97)	Light brown	184	34.88 (34.78)	3.63 (3.56)	12.49 (12.48)	22.61 (22.76)	26.39 (26.42)
Me ₂ Sn(L ³) ₂	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₈ S ₂ (Cl) ₂ Sn (680.26)	Orange	197	42.58 (42.44)	3.86 (3.83)	16.43 (16.50)	19.47 (19.77)	17.66 (17.46)
L ⁴ (EFBMT)	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ SF (250.30)	Creamish	124	52.60 (52.80)	4.30 (4.40)	22.20 (22.40)	20.90 (20.40)	-
Me ₂ SiCl(L ⁴)	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ ClFSSi (342.90)	Light yellow	134	45.62 (45.61)	4.57 (4.67)	16.21 (16.37)	25.38 (25.17)	8.22 (8.18)
Me ₂ Si(L ⁴) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₈ F ₂ S ₂ Si (556.73)	Yellow	141	49.94 (50.00)	4.17 (4.16)	21.32 (21.21)	19.36 (19.33)	5.21 (5.30)
Me ₂ SnCl(L ⁴)	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ ClFSSn (433.52)	Light yellow	166	36.30 (36.06)	3.58 (3.69)	12.87 (12.94)	20.03 (19.92)	27.22 (27.39)
Me ₂ Sn(L ⁴) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₈ F ₂ S ₂ Sn (647.36)	Yellow	173	42.64 (42.68)	3.60 (3.55)	18.13 (18.10)	16.52 (16.52)	19.11 (19.15)

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the ligands HL¹ (EMPCT)

and HL² (EFMT) and their complexes with silicon(IV) and tin(IV) were recorded. The test solutions were pre-

pared by dissolving the ligands and their organosilicon and organotin complexes in dry methanol. Regarding the π - π^* transition in the ligands HL¹ (EMPCT) and HL² (EFMT) the bands observed at 240 nm and 236 nm respectively, which remain unchanged in the spectra of metal complexes. Further the electronic spectra of the ligands HL¹ (EMPCT) and HL² (EFMT) exhibit maxima at 370 nm and 367 nm which can be assigned to the n - π^* transition of the azomethine group. These values undergo a blue shift in the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal complexes and appear at 342 nm {Me₂SiCl(L¹)}, 334 nm {Me₂Si(L¹)₂}, 341 nm {Me₂SiCl(L²)}, 324 nm {Me₂Si(L²)₂}, 362 nm {Me₂SnCl(L¹)}, 355 nm {Me₂Sn(L¹)₂}, 351 nm {Me₂SnCl(L²)}, 348 nm {Me₂Sn(L²)₂}. This blue shift is due to the polarization within the >C=N chromophore group caused by the metal-ligand interaction which clearly indicates the coordination of azomethine nitrogen atom to the metal atom.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of the ligands show a characteristic band due to ν (N-H) at \sim 3250 cm⁻¹. Another band at \sim 1100 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ν (C=S)¹⁸. The deprotonation

of the -N-H moiety of triazole is indicated by the absence of the bands in the spectra of metal complexes at \sim 3250 cm⁻¹ and 1100 cm⁻¹ which appear due to ν (N-H) and ν (C=S) respectively in the spectra of the ligands and appears a new band at \sim 748 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to ν (C-S). This shows the complexation of the metal atom through sulphur atom. Metal-sulphur bond formation is further supported by a band at \sim 412 cm⁻¹ and \sim 455 cm⁻¹ for ν (Sn-S) and ν (Si-S)^{8,19,20} respectively. A sharp and strong band in the region 1617-1601 cm⁻¹ for ν (N=CH)²¹ in case of ligands is shifted to higher wavelength number and appeared in the region 1628-1612 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of metal complexes⁶, indicating coordination through the azomethine nitrogen atom to the metal atom. Formation of a metal-nitrogen bond is further supported by the presence of a band at \sim 535 cm⁻¹ and \sim 570 cm⁻¹ for ν (Si-N)²² and ν (Sn-N)²³ respectively, indicating the coordination of the ligand to the central metal atom through the azomethine nitrogen atom. A strong band in the region of 425-375 cm⁻¹ has been observed due to ν (M-Cl)²⁴. The infrared spectral data of the ligands and their metal complexes are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. IR spectroscopic data (cm⁻¹) of the ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.	ν (N-H)	ν (C=N)	ν (C=S) ^a / ν (C-S) ^b	ν (M-S)	ν (M-N)	ν (M-Cl)
L ¹ (EMPCT)	3257	1617	1096	-	-	-
Me ₂ SiCl(L ¹)	-	1623	747	451	570	422
Me ₂ Si(L ¹) ₂	-	1625	745	457	577	-
Me ₂ SnCl(L ¹)	-	1625	743	405	520	375
Me ₂ Sn(L ¹) ₂	-	1628	744	413	533	-
L ² (EFMT)	3247	1605	1107	-	-	-
Me ₂ SiCl(L ²)	-	1611	753	444	575	418
Me ₂ Si(L ²) ₂	-	1616	758	453	582	-
Me ₂ SnCl(L ²)	-	1617	744	412	531	390
Me ₂ Sn(L ²) ₂	-	1612	742	416	533	-
L ³ (CBEMT)	3255	1601	1091	-	-	-
Me ₂ SiCl(L ³)	-	1613	754	454	568	425
Me ₂ Si(L ³) ₂	-	1611	746	459	577	-
Me ₂ SnCl(L ³)	-	1613	745	405	533	398
Me ₂ Sn(L ³) ₂	-	1611	747	412	542	-
L ⁴ (EFBMT)	3250	1610	1110	-	-	-
Me ₂ SiCl(L ⁴)	-	1616	747	450	577	405
Me ₂ Si(L ⁴) ₂	-	1618	749	456	564	-
Me ₂ SnCl(L ⁴)	-	1621	749	405	525	391
Me ₂ Sn(L ⁴) ₂	-	1616	742	416	535	-

a = Ligands. *b* = Complexes.

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands and their organosilicon and organotin complexes were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard. The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands show the -SH proton signal at δ 13.2 to 13.7 ppm. Disappearance of this signal due to -SH proton in the metal complexes indicates the deprotonation of the thiol group and this supported the coordination of ligand through sulphur atom to the metal atom. The signals of azomethine proton appear at δ 10.3 ppm and δ 9.7 ppm for the ligands HL¹ and HL² respectively. These signals shifted to high field in the spectra of the complexes and appear at δ 9.5–9.7 ppm for organosilicon and organotin complexes of ligand HL¹ and δ 9.1–9.2 ppm for organosilicon and organotin complexes of ligand HL². This indicates the bonding through the azomethine nitrogen atom to the central metal atom. Aromatic protons give signal at δ 6.3–8.5 ppm. Further -CH₂ and -CH₃ moieties of the ethyl group gave signals at δ 2.1–2.8 ppm and δ 1.1–1.3 ppm respectively. The ¹H NMR spectroscopic data of the ligands HL¹ (EMPCT) and HL² (EFMT) and their metal complexes are given in Table 3.

Table 3. ¹H NMR chemical shifts of the ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.	Aromatic-H	-CH ₃	-CH ₂	-CH=N	-SH
L ¹ (EMPCT)	7.6–8.5(m)	1.2(t)	2.8(q)	10.3(s)	13.7(s)
Me ₂ SiCl(L ¹)	7.3–8.3(m)	1.3(t)	2.6(q)	9.7(s)	-
Me ₂ Si(L ¹) ₂	7.1–8.0(m)	1.2(t)	2.5(q)	9.6(s)	-
Me ₂ SnCl(L ¹)	6.9–8.0(m)	1.3(t)	2.7(q)	9.5(s)	-
Me ₂ Sn(L ¹) ₂	7.1–7.9(m)	1.3(t)	2.5(q)	9.5(s)	-
L ² (EFMT)	6.7–7.8(m)	1.1(t)	2.3(q)	9.7(s)	13.2(s)
Me ₂ SiCl(L ²)	6.4–7.2(m)	1.2(t)	2.2(q)	9.2(s)	-
Me ₂ Si(L ²) ₂	6.3–7.3(m)	1.1(t)	2.1(q)	9.1(s)	-
Me ₂ SnCl(L ²)	6.4–7.3(m)	1.3(t)	2.2(q)	9.2(s)	-
Me ₂ Sn(L ²) ₂	6.5–7.4(m)	1.2(t)	2.2(q)	9.2(s)	-

¹³C NMR spectra :

The ¹³C NMR spectral data of ligand HL¹ and its organosilicon and organotin complexes have been recorded and given in Table 4. The ¹³C NMR spectra also support the structures proposed for silicon and tin complexes. The signal due to the carbon atom attached to azomethine nitrogen atom in the ligand appears at δ 163.9 ppm. However in the spectra of the complexes, the signal shifted to the lower δ values and appears at δ 158.8, 159.3, 159.4, 159.2 in case of silicon and tin complexes respectively. This considerable shift in the spectra of metal complexes indicates the coordination of nitrogen to central atom in complexes. Further the shifting of the ¹³C-resonance which is attached to sulphur atom in the spectra of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal complexes compared to free ligand indicates the coordination through sulphur to the metal atom. The new signal due to the methyl group attached to the metal atom in the spectra of metal complexes are also recorded and mentioned in Table 4.

²⁹Si and ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra :

In order to confirm the geometry of the complexes, ²⁹Si and ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra of the organosilicon and organotin complexes of ligand HL¹ were recorded. The value of δ ²⁹Si and ¹¹⁹Sn²⁵ reflects the coordination number of the central metal atom (nucleus) in the corresponding compound. In general ²⁹Si and ¹¹⁹Sn chemical shifts move to lower frequency with increasing coordination number of the nuclei. The spectrum shows in each case only a sharp singlet indicating the formation of single species. ²⁹Si NMR spectra of silicon complexes gave sharp singlets at δ -95.7 ppm and δ -118.1 ppm for {Me₂SiCl(L¹)} and {Me₂Si(L¹)₂} respectively. Similarly ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra of tin complexes gave sharp singlet peaks at δ -148.6 ppm and δ -258.7 ppm for {Me₂SnCl(L¹)}, {Me₂Sn(L¹)₂} respectively. The δ value in this range is an indicative of penta and hexa coordi-

Table 4. ¹³C NMR chemical shifts of the ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.	C ₁			C ₄	C ₅		C ₇	C ₈		C ₁₀	M-CH ₃
L ¹ (EMPCT)	144.1	123.4	131.7	123.4	149.8	163.9	147.4	148.5	25.22	18.29	-
Me ₂ SiCl(L ¹)	144.3	123.6	131.3	123.3	149.6	158.8	147.1	147.2	25.12	18.23	15.0
Me ₂ Si(L ¹) ₂	144.0	123.7	131.4	123.2	149.5	159.3	147.3	147.3	22.86	12.12	18.34
Me ₂ SnCl(L ¹)	144.2	123.5	134.5	123.3	149.6	159.4	147.2	147.2	26.54	15.68	25.63
Me ₂ Sn(L ¹) ₂	144.3	123.6	131.3	123.3	149.6	159.2	143.3	147.1	20.36	15.79	35.14

Fig. 1. Structure of Schiff bases.

Synthesis of organometallic complexes :

(i) Synthesis of 1 : 1 organosilicon complexes :

To the Me_2SiCl_2 (0.200 g, 1.5 mmol) in ~30 ml of dry methanol, was added the sodium salt of the corresponding ligands in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The sodium salts of the ligands were prepared by dissolving the sodium metal (0.036 g, 1.5 mmol) and EMPCT (0.362 g, 1.5 mmol), EFMT (0.344 g, 1.5 mmol), CBEMT (0.413 g, 1.5 mmol) and EFBMT (0.388 g, 1.5 mmol) in ~30 ml dry methanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 12 h and then allowed to cool at room temperature. The excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure by vacuum pump and the resulting solid was repeatedly washed with 5–10 ml dry cyclohexane and again dried under vacuum.

(ii) Synthesis of 1 : 2 organosilicon complexes :

To the Me_2SiCl_2 (0.200 g, 1.5 mmol) in ~30 ml of dry methanol, was added the sodium salt of the corresponding ligands in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The sodium salts of the ligands were prepared by dissolving the sodium metal (0.071 g, 3.0 mmol) and EMPCT (0.723 g, 3.0 mmol), EFMT (0.688 g, 3.0 mmol), CBEMT (0.826 g, 3.0 mmol) and EFBMT (0.775 g, 3.0 mmol) in ~30 ml dry methanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 12 h and then allowed to cool at room temperature. The excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure by vacuum pump and the resulting solid was repeatedly washed with 5–10 ml dry cyclohexane and again dried under vacuum.

Fig. 2. Proposed structures of the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes.

(iii) *Synthesis of 1 : 1 organotin complexes :*

The sodium salts of the ligands were prepared by dissolving the sodium metal (0.021 g, 0.91 mmol) and EMPCT (0.212 g, 0.91 mmol), EFMT (0.202 g, 0.91 mmol), CBEMT (0.243 g, 0.91 mmol) and EFBMT (0.227 g, 0.91 mmol) in ~30 ml dry methanol. Then to the Me_2SnCl_2 (0.200 g, 0.91 mmol) in ~30 ml of dry methanol, the sodium salt of the corresponding ligands in 1 : 1 molar ratio was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 12 h and then allowed to cool at room temperature. The excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure by vacuum pump and the resulting solid was repeatedly washed with 5–10 ml dry cyclohexane and again dried under vacuum.

(iv) *Synthesis of 1 : 2 organotin complexes :*

The sodium salts of the ligands were prepared by dissolving the sodium metal (0.042 g, 1.82 mmol) and EMPCT (0.425 g, 1.82 mmol), EFMT (0.405 g, 1.82 mmol), CBEMT (0.485 g, 1.82 mmol) and EFBMT (0.456 g, 1.82 mmol) in ~30 ml dry methanol. Then to the Me_2SnCl_2 (0.200 g, 0.91 mmol) in ~30 ml of dry methanol, was added the sodium salt of the corresponding ligands in 1 : 2 molar ratio was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 12 h and then allowed to cool at room temperature. The excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure by vacuum pump and the resulting solid was repeatedly washed with 5–10 ml dry cyclohexane and again dried under vacuum. The elemental analysis and physical properties of the complexes are reported in Table 1.

Conclusion :

On the bases of the above mentioned different spectral studies, it is suggested that the deprotonation of thiol group and bonding through sulphur and azomethine nitrogen atoms to silicon and tin central atoms takes place. Finally the geometries around the silicon and tin atoms in the complexes have been suggested as trigonal bipyramidal and octahedral in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes respectively as shown in Fig. 2.

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